

Decoupled Dirac Equations as a Hypergeometric Equation for the Cornell Potential in 3D

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In (1), an exact solution of the Dirac equations is given for the Cornell Potential $V(r)=ar-b/r+cr^*$. In (2), the authors apply the Nikiforov-Uvarov NU method to obtain the same solution. In this note, we use an approach applied in notes (3) and (4) to try to show the Cornell potential is consistent with a hypergeometric equation which has a Rodrigues polynomial solution. In (3) and (4), the one dimensional Dirac equations were considered and solutions of the form $u(x)=u_0(x)u_1(x)$ and $v(x)=v_0(x)v_1(x)$, where u_0 and v_0 are ground state solutions, were examined. It was shown one could eliminate the potential and obtain a second order DE for $v_1(x)$. (Alternatively, this could be done for u_1 .) Forcing this equation to conform to the hypergeometric form yielded a relationship between v_0/u_0 and $V(x)$ the potential. For the 3D case with the Cornell potential, the equations are a little different, but the same method can be applied, it seems. We first try to obtain a second order decoupled DE by using $u(x)=u_0(x)u_1(x)$ etc and then force hypergeometric conditions to show that the Cornell potential is a solution for $V(r)$. It then follows that $u_1(r)$ is given by a Rodrigues polynomial. We again link $V(r)$ to $v_0(r)/u_0(r)$.

Dirac Equations in Spherical Coordinates

In (2), the radial Dirac equations (for a 3D spherical problem) are given by:

$$d/dr u(r) = -k/r u(r) + [E+m] v(r) \quad ((1a))$$

$$d/dr v(r) = k/r v(r) - [E-m-V(r)] u(r) \quad ((1b))$$

k is given in terms of j (see (2) for details).

We use $u(r)=u_0(r)u_1(r)$ and $v(r)=v_0(r)v_1(r)$ where $u_0(r)$ and $v_0(r)$ are ground state solutions and obtain:

$$u_0 d/dr u_1 = (E+m)v_0 v_1 - (E_0+m) u_1 v_0 \quad ((2))$$

((2)) allows one to write $v_1(r)$ in terms of $d/dr u_1$ and u_1 .

and

$$v_0 d/dr v_1 + v_1 d/dr v_0 = k/r v_0 v_1 + u_1 d/dr v_0 - k/r v_0 u_1 \quad ((3))$$

Using $v_1(r)$ written in terms of u_1 in ((3))

$v_1 = u_0 \frac{d}{dr} u_0 \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{v_0} \right) + \left[\frac{E_0+m}{E+m} \right] u_1$ and dv_1/dr in terms of u_1 and $d/dr u_1$

one may obtain a decoupled second order DE for $u_1(r)$.

The coefficients of this second order DE are:

$$\left[\text{coefficient of } \frac{d}{dr} \frac{d}{dr} u_1 \right] = \frac{u_0}{E+m} \quad ((4))$$

$$\left[\text{coefficient of } \frac{d}{dr} u_1 \right] = \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) \frac{d}{dr} \frac{u_0}{u_0} - \left(\frac{d}{dr} \frac{v_0}{v_0} \right) \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{v_0} \right) \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) \left(\frac{d}{dr} v_0 - \frac{k}{r} v_0 \right) + \frac{v_0 (E_0+m)}{E+m} \quad ((5))$$

$$\left[\text{coefficient of } u_1 \right] = \left[\frac{E_0+m}{E+m} \right] \left[\frac{d}{dr} v_0 - \frac{k}{r} v_0 \right] - \frac{d}{dr} \frac{u_0}{u_0} + \frac{k}{r} \frac{v_0}{v_0} \quad ((6))$$

According to (5), one is guaranteed a Rodrigues polynomial solution if the second order DE is of the form:

$$p(r) \frac{d}{dr} \frac{d}{dr} u_1 + q(r) \frac{d}{dr} u_1 + \text{constant } u_1 = 0 \quad ((7))$$

where $p(r)$ is at most quadratic in r and $q(r)$ linear. In (5), the Rodrigues polynomial solution and eigenvalue formulas are given.

We take (4), (5) and (6) and divide by $u_0(r)$. Then, $p(r)$, the coefficient of $d/dr d/dr u_1$, is $1/(E+m)$ which is a quadratic or lower. The coefficient of u_1 must be a constant. Using ((2)) to replace $[d/dr v_0 / u_0 - k/r v_0 / u_0]$ and ((3)) to replace $d/dr u_0 / u_0$ yields:

$$\left\{ -C_1 + \frac{k}{r} - \left[\frac{E_0+m}{E+m} \right] (E-m-V(r)) \right\} / \left\{ E+m - \frac{k}{r} \right\} = \frac{v_0}{u_0} \quad ((8))$$

Next, the coefficient of $d/dr u_1$ should equal $ar+b$ or:

$$\left(\frac{v_0}{u_0} \right) \left[\frac{E_0+m}{E+m} \right] + \left(\frac{d}{dr} \frac{u_0}{u_0} \right) \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) - \frac{k}{r} \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) = ar+b \quad ((9))$$

Using: $d/dr u_0 \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) = -\frac{k}{r} \frac{u_0}{E+m} + v_0$ yields:

$$ar+b = \left(\frac{v_0}{u_0} \right) \left[\frac{E_0+m}{E+m} \right] - \frac{2k}{r} \left(\frac{1}{E+m} \right) + \frac{v_0}{u_0}$$

Let $r=1/x$ where $1/x$ is small and $B = \left[\frac{E_0+m}{E+m} \right]$. Then:

$$a/x + b = -2kx + [B+1] \{ B(E-m-V) + kx - C \} / \{ E+m - kx \}$$

If one considers V to be a polynomial in x and looks for the highest order of x one has:

$$\text{RHS } O(x^*x) \quad \text{LHS } V^*x + x^*x^*x$$

Thus, V should be of the order of x^*x to cancel with x^*x^*x because there is no $O(x^*x^*x)$ on the RHS. In other words, one has:

$$V(x) = a_1 + b_1 x + c_1 x^*x \quad ((10))$$

This is the same result as (2). Noting that $x=1/r$ one would first conclude that:

$$V(r) = a_1 + b_1/r + c_1/(r^*r)$$

The authors of (2), however, argue one may use: $r = 1/x$ but consider an expansion in powers of around $1/r_0$, which they call a meson radius.. They then argue that $V(x)=a_1 + b_1 x + c_1 x^*x$ is equivalent to:

$$V(r) = ar - b/r + cr^*r, \text{ the Cornell potential.}$$

(We leave these details to (2) and its references as these authors have a specific model in mind it seems. This model, however, only applies to $V(r)$. Terms such as k/r become kx according to $x=1/r$.)

Conclusion

In (2), the Nikiforov-Uvarov method is applied to the radial Dirac equations for a Cornell potential. The first step is to combine the two equations into one decoupled one for u . Next, a change of variables is made using $r=1/x$ to bring the equations into the NU form. (The derivatives d/dr d/dr , d/dr and terms such as $1/r$ and $1/(r^*r)$ transform in a regular way using $r=1/x$. The Cornell potential, however, is transformed in a slightly different manner. See (2).)

In this note, we have tried to present an alternative method. We use $u(r)=u_0(r)u_1(r)$ and $v(r)=v_0(r)v_1(r)$ where u_0 and v_0 are ground state solutions. We find a decoupled second order DE for $u_1(r)$ and immediately apply the conditions of a general hypergeometric equation. By linking v_0/u_0 to $V(r)$ we try to show that a Cornell potential (in the context used in (2)) applies. A Rodrigues polynomial solution with eigenvalues is then guaranteed from formulas given in (5).

References

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